
ABSTRACT

Parents have become more concerned for child. In nuclear families parents pay more attention on child education; they plan school, college, career after discussion with field experts. Such consciousness increases their intention towards quality education. Parents belonging nuclear family pay more money rather than conventional family. They have financial plan also regarding study. In other families attention on child is distributed and unable to concentrate child only. This social trend influence child performance and quality education.

KEYWORDS: Nuclear family, urbanization, cooperative attitude, consciousness.

INTRODUCTION

The data in the recent census report that the nuclear family system is rapidly replacing the joint family system, indicating a visible breakdown of traditional family structures in the country. The new census report puts the average household size at 4.88, a remarkable decrease from the 5.44 that was recorded 10 years ago. Urbanisation, migration, education, imitation of western values and declining fertility rates are factors seen as being responsible for this new trend.

The child of school going age and the adolescent of college going age represent almost 30 percent of the population. Of the approximately 19.39 crore children in the elementary education age group about 14.71 crore are enrolled in schools. In the present days the family structure has changed drastically. Now with decrease in the members in the family, the attention for the betterment of livelihood has increase. Now the focus on educational concerns has tended to marginalize the other dimensions of quality. Some of these dimensions are Health & Education. The parents are determined for the quality education of their children as they could focus on education effectively.

Family structure is conceptualized as the configuration of role, power and status, and relationships in the family. The nuclear type of family is the one, in which the group consists of a male, his wife and their children. The trend of the quality education depends on the structure and the size of the family. Family joint ness still continues to be major sociological phenomena. Kapadia, K.M. (1966) has defined a joint family as; "they should dwell in the same house, take their meals and perform their worship together and enjoy property in common". Common residence and joint preparation of food as well as eating together were the external symbols of homogeneity of the family.

It is a believe that a nuclear family is the best arrangement, yielding numerous advantages. It is common to have dual incomes in nuclear family. Both parents work to provide financial stability for the household, creating a larger cash flow to supply the basic family needs of housing, food and healthcare. Financial stability also allows the parents to provide additional extracurricular opportunities for their children, such as music or athletic lessons. These opportunities allow children to flourish socially and develop a higher level of confidence. A 2-parent household is more likely to have a higher consistency with raising their children. By reaching agreements on discipline and modeling appropriate behavior, parents act as a team to strengthen and reinforce child behavior. Children get consistent messages about behavioral expectations. Nuclear families have more daily routines, like eating dinner

together, adding to consistency. Nuclear families tend to establish stronger bonds as they work together and rely on one another to overcome challenges. Children witness their parents supportive and loving relationships, which help them, learn how to interact appropriately. Nuclear families tend to be more resilient when faced with obstacles, as they learn to problem solve together and support each other emotionally.

Family Environment influence student's psychologically. His personality, education, career, cultural, moral values are based on family environment. Students studying up to 11th class are more influenced rather than other students as they are younger. Traditional family makes a supportive environment inculcating moral, family, social, cultural values and dependency on other family members. Nuclear family makes a self depend environment where student has to do his own work. Parents are unable to give sufficient time to child to support him and for development of social, cultural, moral values.

METHODOLOGY

A survey was conducted with the student studying in class up to 11th. 160 students of 6 educational institutes of Jabalpur District were selected randomly for this study. Collected data was divided according to age group as 6 to 9 year old, 10-12 year old, 13-15 year old, and 16-18 year old. Student performance as interest in participation in activities, sincerity for study, cooperative attitude, responsible attitude, devotion for study, work spirit, financial support are studied in respect of family structure.

Findings:

Collected data show that nuclear family trend is increasing every year.

Table-1: Nuclear family trend status in last 3 years

Family	In 2011-12 %	In 2012-13 %	In 2013-14 %
Nuclear Family	21	24	28

Data collected from survey

Chart-1: Nuclear family trend status in last 3 years

Table-2: Student Performance % belonging nuclear family in respect of Quality Tools

Quality Tools	6-9 Year Age	10-12 Year Age	13-15 Year Age	16-18 Year Age
Participation in activities	82	80	77	73
Sincerity for study	78	75	73	62
Cooperative attitude	64	65	68	71
Responsible attitude	41	52	62	77
Devotion for morality	66	63	62	58
Work spirit	61	63	66	74
Financial Support	88	85	81	78

Source: Data received from questionnaire survey from Schools

Table-3: Student performance % belonging Combined Family in respect of Quality Tools

Quality Tools	6-9 Year Age	10-12 Year Age	13-15 Year Age	16-18 Year Age
Participation in activities	78	75	71	65
Sincerity for study	72	69	62	53
Cooperative attitude	71	78	86	93
Responsible attitude	62	68	75	79
Devotion for Morality	67	65	62	59
Work spirit	68	71	73	76
Financial Support	77	72	64	51

Source: Data received from questionnaire survey from Schools

Chart-2: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of participation of activities

Chart-3: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Sincerity for study

Chart-4: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Cooperative attitude

Chart-5: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Responsible attitude

Chart-6: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Devotion for Morality

Chart-7: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Work spirit

Chart-8: Comparison of joint family and nuclear family child in respect of Financial Support

ANALYSIS

Data regarding comparison of last 3 years trend shows that trend of nuclear family is increasing. In the year 2011-12, 21% family was nuclear family but in 2012-13 increased and reached up to 24%. In the year 2013-14, 28% families are searched as nuclear family.

Participation in activity related data of joint family and nuclear family shows that % of involvement decrease with increase in age. Nuclear family child participation in activities is higher than joint family child.

Comparison for sincerity towards study related data indicates that with the increase in age, % of student involvement decrease. For joint family kids, sincerity found 72% in 6-9 year students and it declined up to 53% for child of 16-18 year age. While for nuclear family students, sincerity decrease from 78% to 62% in same order. Sincerity is higher at all age level in nuclear family kids.

Quality tool cooperative attitude related data exhibits that with the age student attitude changed positively i.e., cooperative attitude % increase with age. In joint family child this tool is found 71% for 6-9 year age students and 78% for 10-12 year students. For age group 13-15 years 86% and for 16-18 year 93% cooperative attitude found. In nuclear family cooperative attitude is less in comparison.

Responsibility attitude value is higher in joint family students and in both category responsibility is increasing with the age. In joint family students, for the age group 6-9 years, responsibility found 62%, 68% for 10-12 year age group, 75% for 13-15 year and 79% for 16-18 year students. In nuclear family, responsibility attitude varies from 41% to 77%.

Devotion for morality is found higher for age group 6-9 year students. In both category students, as age is increasing devotion value is decreasing. Comparison shows that value % is nearly similar.

Work spirit value is increasing with age in both category. For nuclear family kids work spirit value is higher rather than joint family kids and value varied from 68% to 76%. For joint family students variation is observed from 61% to 74%.

In case of nuclear family kids, family financial support found is higher rather than joint family kids. In nuclear family, for 6-9 year students, financial support is 88% and decrease up to 78% for 16-18 year students. In joint family cases, financial support % decrease from 77% to 51%.

CONCLUSION

This trend related data shows how nuclear family environment is positive for development of students. Student being member of nuclear family got 5% more chances for participation in activities, sincerity for study is higher 8% rather than child of joint family. In the matter of devotion for study nuclear family student is 15% more devoted. On the other hand cooperative and responsible attitude is found 15% and 13% higher in joint family student respectively. Work spirit has marked 6% more in joint family environment. The important factor is financial support which is marked in survey study as 17% higher in nuclear family. Development of these characters in students is important part of quality education institute management.

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